

Appendix – Dynamic Agent Generation for Self-Adaptive Root Cause Analysis

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1 Overview

This appendix accompanies the paper “*Dynamic Agent Generation for Self-Adaptive Root Cause Analysis*”, accepted to SEAMS 2026. It provides extended experimental results, ablation tables, parameter analyses, and dataset statistics. All scripts, and raw results are available in our public replication package: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18302941>.

1.1 Example Query and Buildspec

Query Example. *On March 4, 2021, between 18:30 and 19:00, a failure occurred. However, the root cause component, the exact time of the root cause occurrence, and the underlying reason for the failure are currently unknown. You are tasked with identifying the root cause component, the root cause occurrence datetime, and the root cause reason.*

Listing 1: Example Buildspec

```
{
  "task_type": "task_7",
  "date": "2021-03-04",
  "filename_date": "2021_03_04",
  "failure_time_range": {
    "start": "18:30:00",
    "end": "19:00:00"
  },
  "failure_time_range_ts": {
    "start": 1614853800,
    "end": 1614855600
  },
  "failures_detected": 1,
  "uncertainty": {
    "root_cause_time": "unknown",
    "root_cause_component": "unknown",
    "root_cause_reason": "unknown"
  },
  "objective": "Identify the root cause component, the exact root cause datetime and reason for the failure",
  "filename_date_directory": "/agentfactory/data/Bank/telemetry/2021_03_04",
  "absolute_log_file": "/agentfactory/data/Bank/telemetry/2021_03_04/log/log_service.csv",
  "absolute_trace_file": "/agentfactory/data/Bank/telemetry/2021_03_04/trace/trace_span.csv",
  "absolute_metrics_file": "/agentfactory/data/Bank/telemetry/2021_03_04/metric/metric_container.csv"
}
```

1.2 Agent and Tool templates

Listing 2: Metrics Analyst Agent Template

```
1 metrics_analyst_agent:
2   role: >
3     Specialist agent dedicated to analyzing system metrics for Root Cause
4     Analysis (RCA).
5     It focuses exclusively on metric files (metric_app.csv and metric_container
6     .csv)
7     to detect anomalies, identify faulty components, and narrow down the search
8     space for RCA.
9
10  goal: |
11    - Parse and preprocess metric data for the specified time window.
12    - Compute global thresholds (e.g., P95, P90, P15, P5) for each KPI across
13    all components.
14    - Detect anomalies by comparing KPI values against thresholds.
15    - Identify faulty components by grouping consecutive anomalies into faults.
16    - Filter out noise (isolated spikes, borderline threshold breaches).
17    - Produce a list of candidate faulty components and time ranges for further
18    trace/log analysis.
19
20  backstory: >
21    You are an observability and performance monitoring expert specialized in
22    time-series metrics.
23    You understand system KPIs such as CPU usage, memory, latency, and error
24    rates.
25    Your role is to transform raw numbers into actionable insights: which
26    component is failing,
27    when, and how severely. You strictly follow the global threshold
28    methodology defined in the
29    failure diagnosis rules to ensure reliability and consistency across RCA
30    analyses.
31
32  constraints: |
33    - Do not use logs or traces. Your scope is metrics only.
34    - Always calculate global thresholds using the entire metric file before
35    filtering.
36    - Never misinterpret isolated spikes as faults.
37    - Work in UTC+8 when handling timestamps.
38    - Ensure outputs comply with the expected JSON schema.
```

Listing 3: DataFrame Cutter Tool

```
1 class DataFrameCutterTool(BaseTool):
2     name: str = "dataframe_cutter"
3     description: str = (
4         "Slices a Pandas DataFrame according to a UNIX timestamp interval (
5         start, stop). "
6         "The DataFrame must contain a 'timestamp' column. "
7         "Returns the result in CSV format (UTF-8). "
8     )
9
10    def _run(self, start: int, stop: int, input_df: pd.DataFrame) -> str:
11        if input_df is None:
12            raise ValueError("input_df must be provided and cannot be None")
13        if "timestamp" not in input_df.columns:
14            raise ValueError("input_df must contain a 'timestamp' column")
15
16        df_cut = input_df[
17            (input_df["timestamp"] >= start) &
18            (input_df["timestamp"] <= stop)
19        ]
```

```

19 csv_buffer = io.StringIO()
20 chunk_size = 100000
21
22
23 if len(df_cut) > chunk_size:
24     for i in range(0, len(df_cut), chunk_size):
25         df_cut.iloc[i:i + chunk_size].to_csv(
26             csv_buffer, index=False, header=(i == 0)
27         )
28     else:
29         df_cut.to_csv(csv_buffer, index=False)
30
31     return csv_buffer.getvalue()
32
33 async def _arun(self, *args, **kwargs):
34     raise NotImplementedError("Async execution is not implemented")

```

2 Extended Results (RQ1)

Table 1: Accuracy comparison across OpenRCA datasets—Telecom, Bank, Market

Max. Agents	Method	Telecom		Bank		Market		Partial	Correct
		Partial	Correct	Partial	Correct	Partial	Correct		
N/A	RCA-Agent(Claude 3.5)	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	11.34	17.31
N/A	RCA-Agent(GPT-4o)	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	8.96	17.96
N/A	RCA-Agent(Gemini1.5 Pro)	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	2.69	6.87
N/A	RCA-Agent(Llama 3.1 Instr.)	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	3.28	5.65
5	Claude 3.5	7.42 ± 2.41	8.36 ± 2.58	9.01 ± 2.72	6.58 ± 2.13	7.94 ± 2.46	8.62 ± 2.61	8.12 ± 2.53	7.85 ± 2.44
	GPT-4o	6.85 ± 2.27	8.11 ± 2.49	8.78 ± 2.65	6.24 ± 2.08	7.63 ± 2.42	8.21 ± 2.56	7.75 ± 2.45	7.52 ± 2.38
	Gemini 1.5 Pro	5.97 ± 2.04	7.22 ± 2.31	7.81 ± 2.48	5.36 ± 1.96	6.48 ± 2.22	7.09 ± 2.37	6.75 ± 2.16	6.56 ± 2.21
	Mistral Large 2	3.54 ± 1.88	4.86 ± 2.07	5.12 ± 2.14	3.11 ± 1.74	4.25 ± 1.96	4.73 ± 2.05	4.30 ± 1.99	4.23 ± 1.95
	Llama 70B	2.97 ± 1.73	3.75 ± 1.89	4.16 ± 2.01	2.68 ± 1.62	3.44 ± 1.83	3.97 ± 1.92	3.52 ± 1.79	3.47 ± 1.81
	Llama 8B	0.00 ± 0.00	0.00 ± 0.00	0.00 ± 0.00	0.00 ± 0.00	0.00 ± 0.00	0.00 ± 0.00	0.00 ± 0.00	0.00 ± 0.00
	Mistral 7B	0.00 ± 0.00	0.00 ± 0.00	0.00 ± 0.00	0.00 ± 0.00	0.00 ± 0.00	0.00 ± 0.00	0.00 ± 0.00	0.00 ± 0.00
10	Claude 3.5	35.41 ± 2.12	29.86 ± 1.73	33.25 ± 2.05	27.63 ± 2.05	32.44 ± 2.41	29.18 ± 2.27	33.70 ± 1.97	28.89 ± 1.82
	GPT-4o	31.78 ± 1.66	34.17 ± 1.88	36.12 ± 1.99	30.54 ± 2.23	28.79 ± 2.14	31.07 ± 2.34	32.23 ± 1.92	31.93 ± 2.15
	Gemini 1.5 Pro	28.92 ± 1.89	27.51 ± 1.67	30.08 ± 1.84	22.47 ± 1.74	25.36 ± 1.88	26.92 ± 2.16	28.12 ± 1.87	25.63 ± 1.86
	Mistral Large 2	33.07 ± 1.97	30.94 ± 1.91	32.66 ± 1.95	24.62 ± 2.18	23.41 ± 2.10	22.81 ± 2.11	29.71 ± 2.01	26.12 ± 2.07
	Llama 70B	26.38 ± 1.52	25.03 ± 1.59	27.47 ± 1.63	19.85 ± 1.91	21.64 ± 2.02	20.54 ± 1.97	25.16 ± 1.72	21.81 ± 1.83
	Llama 8B	0.44 ± 0.12	0.53 ± 0.14	0.61 ± 0.15	0.51 ± 0.13	0.67 ± 0.16	0.42 ± 0.11	0.57 ± 0.14	0.49 ± 0.13
	Mistral 7B	0.62 ± 0.15	0.39 ± 0.11	0.35 ± 0.09	0.36 ± 0.09	0.47 ± 0.12	0.58 ± 0.14	0.48 ± 0.12	0.44 ± 0.11
20	Claude 3.5	34.92 ± 2.71	30.11 ± 2.18	34.02 ± 2.95	28.14 ± 2.44	31.88 ± 2.87	29.87 ± 2.63	33.61 ± 2.84	29.37 ± 2.43
	GPT-4o	32.43 ± 2.54	33.28 ± 2.33	35.76 ± 2.81	31.08 ± 2.69	29.21 ± 2.25	30.92 ± 2.77	32.47 ± 2.53	31.76 ± 2.60
	Gemini 1.5 Pro	27.85 ± 2.42	28.63 ± 2.16	31.45 ± 2.74	23.04 ± 2.31	24.92 ± 2.68	26.35 ± 2.52	28.74 ± 2.61	26.67 ± 2.46
	Mistral Large 2	34.12 ± 2.85	29.83 ± 2.29	31.88 ± 2.79	25.17 ± 2.47	22.96 ± 2.41	23.64 ± 2.63	29.65 ± 2.68	26.21 ± 2.46
	Llama 70B	25.97 ± 2.18	26.48 ± 2.31	27.21 ± 2.54	20.36 ± 2.25	22.05 ± 2.44	21.12 ± 2.39	25.74 ± 2.36	21.84 ± 2.36
	Llama 8B	0.53 ± 0.21	0.49 ± 0.19	0.57 ± 0.23	0.47 ± 0.18	0.59 ± 0.22	0.51 ± 0.20	0.56 ± 0.20	0.49 ± 0.19
	Mistral 7B	0.48 ± 0.19	0.57 ± 0.24	0.43 ± 0.18	0.55 ± 0.23	0.41 ± 0.17	0.46 ± 0.21	0.44 ± 0.18	0.49 ± 0.22

Note: Green cells denote proprietary LLMs with the highest precision; Blue cells denote large LLMs with strong precision; Purple cells denote smaller LLMs with lower precision.

Figure 1: Comparison of correct OpenRCA results for sequential (left) and asynchronous (right) execution mode.

(a) OpenRCA — Partial (Sequential)

(b) OpenRCA — Partial (Asynchrone)

Figure 2: Comparison of partial OpenRCA results for sequential (left) and asynchronous (right) execution mode.

(a) Nezha-OB — PR@1

(b) Nezha-TT — PR@1

(c) Nezha-OB — PR@3

(d) Nezha-TT — PR@3

(e) Nezha-OB — PR@5

(f) Nezha-TT — PR@5

Figure 3: Comparison of precision for asynchronous execution modes of the Nezha-OB (left) and Nezha-TT (right).

(a) Nezha-OB — PR@1

(b) Nezha-TT — PR@1

(c) Nezha-OB — PR@3

(d) Nezha-TT — PR@3

(e) Nezha-OB — PR@5

(f) Nezha-TT — PR@5

Figure 4: Comparison of precision for sequential execution modes of the Nezha-OB (left) and Nezha-TT (right).

Figure 5: Precision@K vs number of adapted agents across Nezha-OB (left) and Nezha-TT (right).

Figure 6: Accuracy vs number of adapted agents OpenRCA Partial (left) and OpenRCA Correct (right).